

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A DEMOGRAPHIC HEALTH SURVEY TO COMPARE
COMPLETE AND INCOMPLETE IMMUNISATION IN
CHILDREN REGARDING VARIOUS CONTRIBUTING
VARIABLES****Dr. Hafiza Madeeha Latif, Dr. Maria Ghafoor, Dr. Rabbia Bajwa**
Allied Hospital Faisalabad**Abstract:**

Objective: The research objective is to measure the immunization of Pakistani children with respect to various contributing variables.

Methods: Health survey and demographic data of Pakistan was analysed at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (December 2016 to June 2017). Children who could not obtain all doses were reported as immunized incompletely. Binary logistic regression (simple and multi-variable) were used for the assessment of the association of determinants.

Results: Mean age of mothers and fathers was respectively (32.70 ± 8.6) years and (37.90 ± 10.10) years. In bivariate analysis, incomplete immunization was significantly associated with distant healthcare facility, mother's age above 35 years, rural population, home deliveries, last born in birth order greater than seven, no visit by LHW in last one year and female sex. The outcome of last multinomial regression analysis shows no visit in the last 12 months by LHW to be the most significant risk factor.

Conclusions: The research outcome concludes that visit by LHW in the last twelve months has a significant association with immunization.

Keywords: Lady Health Worker (LHW), World Health Organization (WHO), Determinants, Immunization.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Hafiza Madeeha Latif,
Allied Hospital,
Faisalabad

QR code

Please cite this article in press Hafiza Madeeha Latif *et al.*, A Demographic Health Survey to Compare Complete and Incomplete Immunisation in Children Regarding Various Contributing Variables., *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2018; 05(09).

INTRODUCTION:

WHO supposed the last year as vaccination decade; however, the objective is still ahead and is to be achieved [1]. Generally, under-5 deaths have reduced from twelve to 6.5 million through WHO efforts. Pakistan's rank in under five years age mortalities is at 26th with 86/1000 mortality rate. Moreover, Pakistan has neonatal and infant mortality rate of 42/1000 and 69/1000 live births respectively [1]. WHO initiated the Exposed Program of Immunization in response to such vaccine-preventable mortalities, and to achieve the goal of reducing child mortality (Millennium Development Goal 4) [2]. Despite this, due to the inaccessibility of health facilities, social problems, and lack of awareness among communities, immunization has still not equally distributed. The government of Pakistan launched the LHW program to deal with this problem in rural areas but uneducated communities were reluctant to have an interaction. A study in 2007 in Pakistan reported that birth rate at home caused 66% incomplete immunization due to community outreach [3]. Services at the doorstep by LHW showed significant improvement by completing 60% of the rural population [4]. In 2005, a randomized control trial carried out in 07 sub-districts of Pakistan, showed lesser number of maternal and perinatal death due to LHW health facilities [5]. A USAID survey (2012) states full immunization among the poorer community by LHWs [6]. Later on, according to 2008 survey at Karachi, LHW program faced many struggles and challenges like lack of incentives, flaws in vaccination mobility, job dissatisfaction and lack of interest of staff and doctors [7]. According to a study in 2008, Rawalpindi states that job dissatisfaction among LHWs is caused by long travel distances, low pay, inconsistent medical supply, lack of career structure and inadequate stipends [8]. LHWs in Pakistan is has a vital role because most of the population lives in rural area. LHWs play a significant role in Supplemental Immunization Activities and Polio Eradication Initiative hence this study emphasizes their association with incomplete immunization.

METHODS:

Health survey and demographic data of Pakistan was analysed at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (December 2016 to June 2017). Children who could not obtain all doses were reported as immunized incompletely. Binary logistic regression (simple and multi-variable) were used for the assessment of the association of determinants. The survey includes unbiased data on variables related to health like mother-child nutrition status and health, awareness of communicable

diseases, and immunization. The survey estimated 13944 participants but the final sample size consisted 96% households (12,943). Information on survey methodology can be found elsewhere [9]. The selection of our study included immunization of age 12 – 23 months' children, resulting in 3,294 as the sample size. We selected this age group because Vaccine-preventable basic course disease and Measles vaccination are completed by the age of 9 and 15 months respectively. Previous studies selected the same age group for the assessment of immunization [10 – 12]. The status of immunization was computed with 05 vaccines, and its 12 doses, i.e DPT and HBV (03), measles and BCG (01) and polio (04). We selected 12 variables, DPT and HBV (1 – 3), polio and BCG (0 – 4) and measles with 4-response categories each i.e. Vaccination date not mentioned, don't know (coded as "0" meaning vaccination not received), and reported by mother, mark of vaccination on card (coded as "1" meaning vaccination received). Later we allotted "immunization status" of all 12-vaccine variables to each child as "1" and "0" considered as "complete" and "incomplete" immunization respectively. "Complete immunization" included 03 DPT doses to prevent Pertussis, tetanus and diphtheria, 01 BCG dose against tuberculosis, 03 polio vaccine doses and 01 measles vaccine dose. Missing all or any of vaccines was considered "Incomplete immunization". This categorization was adopted from previous studies [13 – 15].

Independent variables of our research included: age and education of fathers and mothers, occupation of fathers and index of wealth, gender and children birth order, multiple or single gestation, residence area, time since first cohabitation, antenatal care use, information access, place of delivery, distance to health care facility, and visit of healthcare respondents' in last 12 months.

SPSS was used for data analyzation. Immunization outcomes of children were shown as percentage and frequency distribution. Simple binary logistic regression was used to present independent variables' relationship and its outcome of interest. P-values, odds ratios, and confidence interval of 95% were calculated for dependent and independent variables association. Relationship of LHW visit in last twelve months and immunization status were assessed through logistic regression. Model one included the adjustment of independent variables with multinomial logistic regressions, mode 2 and 3 included the assessment of association of interest, adjusting age of mothers and fathers, their education and index of wealth respectively. In model 4, a

relationship assessment was carried out by adjusting region, place or residence. Model 5 included adjustment of child related variables, like gender, order of birth and multi-gestation. Independent variable related maternal, like place of health care facility and delivery. In our final model, seven, we included all independent variables and evaluated its association of interest. Highly correlated variables were also found and eliminated through the assessment of variables. Between mother's age, between residence and index, Multi-collinearity was assessed through Pearson correlation, which resulted significant 0.01 level. For the national representation of estimate, sample weights were used for all analysis.

RESULTS:

The mean age of fathers and mothers was 37.90 (SD+10) and 32.70 (SD+8.60) respectively. The decrease in parents' education increased the number of incomplete immunizations. Children of fathers

above 35 or more years, who were a manual worker, were incompletely immunized (49%). Female child, higher birth order children (seven or more) 51%, low wealth index 54%, residing at rural place 75% were immunized incompletely. Respondents with the place of delivery home and those who received no visit from LHW during last twelve months had children incompletely immunized. In bivariate analysis, incomplete immunization was significantly associated with distant healthcare facility, mother's age above 35 years, rural population, home deliveries, last born in birth order greater than seven, no visit by LHW in last one year and female sex. The outcome of last multinomial regression analysis shows no visit in the last 12 months by LHW to be the most significant risk factor. We assessed multi-collinearity between wealth and residence index, and between the age of mother through Pearson correlation which had a significant level of 0.01. In the last model, the analysis showed no visit of LHW in the last twelve months has significant risk factor.

Table – I: Percentage and Frequency of Various Variables in Case of Incomplete Immunization

Variables	Number	Percentage	
Mother's Age	> 35	420	20.7
	25 - 34	1135	56
	15 - 24	741	23.3
Father's Age	> 35	943	47.2
	25 - 34	921	46.1
	15 - 24	134	6.7
Mother's Education	Higher Level	127	6.3
	Upper Secondary	277	13.7
	Upper Primary	328	16.2
	No Education	1293	63.8
Father's Education	Higher Level	264	13.1
	Upper Secondary	629	31.2
	Upper Primary	320	16
	No Education	800	39.7
Father's Occupation	Management	121	6
	Clerk	469	23.2
	Worker	993	49
	Agriculture	399	19.7
	Not Working	42	2.1
Place of Residence	Urban	509	25.1
	Rural	1517	74.9
Child Sex	Male	983	48.5

	Female	1044	51.5
Birth Order	1 to 3	1058	52.2
	4 to 6	639	31.6
	Above 7	329	16.2
Wealth Index	Rich	574	28.31
	Middle	359	17.72
	Poor	1092	53.87
Access to Information	Yes	913	47.4
	No	1011	52.6
Place of Delivery	Private Hospital	653	32.3
	Public Hospital	244	12.1
	Home	1123	55.6
Antenatal Care Use	Yes	1378	68.2
	No	643	31.8
Twin Births	Single	2014	99.4
	> 1	12	0.6
Last 12 Months LHW Visit	Yes	683	51.7
	No	639	48.3
Health Facility Visit	Yes	1676	82.9
	No	347	17.1
Distance from Healthcare Center	No Issue	1075	53.2
	Big Issue	945	46.8

Table – I: Percentage and Frequency of Various Variables in Case of Complete Immunization

Variables		Number	Percentage
Mother's Age	> 35	217	18.7
	25 - 34	683	58.8
	15 - 24	261	22.5
Father's Age	> 35	547	47.5
	25 - 34	539	46.8
	15 - 24	65	5.7
Mother's Education	Higher Level	176	15.2
	Upper Secondary	326	28.1
	Upper Primary	190	16.4
	No Education	467	40.3
Father's Education	Higher Level	265	23
	Upper Secondary	459	39.6
	Upper Primary	166	14.4
	No Education	266	23
Father's Occupation	Management	133	11.5
	Clerk	305	56.3
	Worker	591	51
	Agriculture	121	10.4
	Not Working	9	0.8
Place of Residence	Urban	471	40.6

	Rural	689	59.4
Child Sex	Male	615	52.9
	Female	546	47.1
Birth Order	1 to 3	748	64.5
	4 to 6	307	26.5
	Above 7	105	9
Wealth Index	Rich	618	53.3
	Middle	230	19.8
	Poor	312	26.9
Access to Information	Yes	314	28.5
	No	788	71.5
Place of Delivery	Private Hospital	521	45
	Public Hospital	231	19.9
	Home	408	35.1
Antenatal Care Use	Yes	976	84.1
	No	184	15.9
Twin Births	Single	1151	99.1
	> 1	10	0.9
Last 12 Months LHW Visit			
	Yes	635	68.8
	No	288	31.2
Health Facility Visit	Yes	992	85.5
	No	168	14.5
Distance from Healthcare Center	No Issue	872	75.2
	Big Issue	288	24.8

DISCUSSION:

LHW's concept is Chinese Mao Tse Tung (Barefoot doctors) who were peasants trained for medical duties to achieve equal healthcare facilities [16]. In September 1978, health became human right [17]. Since then, Community Health Workers to perform health coverage duties. Child vaccination is most feasible health intervention for the general public [17]. Pakistan has more than 100 thousand LHWs, making it the largest health workers communities in the world [18]. Due to the absence of LHW during last 12 months, thousands of children die from preventable diseases. Mothers find talking to LHWs comfortable and LHWs are the main source of information for them. According to a survey, 72.7% of mothers receive immunization information from LHWs [18]. According to our survey. A study shows that due to the struggles of LHWs, the percentage of children with incomplete immunization reduced from 47% 2001-02) to 22% 2008-09) [20]. This amazing success was possible due to good interaction with households, cost-effectiveness, and community acceptability [21]. However, an Indian research by Arnab and Ashlesha (2007) states no association of LHWs and increase in childhood immunization [22]. Maternal health and reducing child mortality were the main two goals of Millennium Development Goals [22]. According to a study carried in Punjab Pakistan (2006) child mortality rate reduced from

250 to 79 per 100 thousand live births [23]. An Indian study shows reduced neonatal mortality due to visits by LHW to home [24]. A study carried out at Karachi, Pakistan shows that low maternal education is associated with incomplete immunization [25]. A study in Nigeria found 13.10% incomplete immunization of children among formally educated mothers compared to 61.10% among uneducated mothers [2]. The same way, a study in Uganda showed decreased incomplete immunization among educated maternal [27]. In Egypt, a study shows contrary results with 53.60% incomplete immunization among highly educated mothers compared to 50% of illiterate maternal [28]. Longer distance from health centres increases incomplete immunization. This point is supported by the study of Root et al. [29].

CONCLUSION:

The association of the LHW visit in last twelve months with children immunization under two years of age is significant in Pakistan. LHW program must be improved through focused training, sustaining on-going programs, incentives, and initiating new programs so that the rate of mortalities in infants especially in underprivileged areas should be reduced.

REFERENCES:

1. Mary AN, Rosemary S. State of evaluation: Community Health Worker. *Public Health Nursing* 2003;20(4):260-270.
2. Baqui, Abdullah H. Impact of An Integrated Nutrition and Health Programme on Neonatal Mortality in Rural Northern India. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2008;796-804A.
3. Mothers Knowledge About EPI and Its Relation with Age- Appropriate Vaccination of Infants in Peri-Urban Karachi. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2016;3(4):12-6.
4. Oyefara J L. Mother's Characteristics and Immunization Status of Under-Five Children in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State, Nigeria. *SAGE Open.* 2014;4(3):46-9.
5. Bbaale E. Factors Influencing Childhood Immunization in Uganda. *Journal of Health Population and Nutrition.* 2013;118;31(1):54-8.
6. Rahman T. Mothers' Awareness and Knowledge of Under Five Years Children Regarding Immunization in Minia City Egypt. *Research Gate.* 2013. Web. 2 Apr. 2016.
7. Root E, Lucero M, Nohynek H, Anthamatten P, Thomas D, Tallo V et al. Distance to health services affects local-level vaccine efficacy for pneumococcal conjugate vaccine (PCV) among rural Filipino children. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2014;111(9):3520-3525.
8. USAID Research and Development Solutions: Policy Briefs Series No.3, February 2012 http://resdv.org/files/policy_brief/3/3.pdf retrieved on 12-2-2015
9. Mangrio N, Alam M, Shaikh B. Is Expanded Programme on Immunization doing enough? Viewpoint of Health workers and Managers in Sindh, Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2008; 58:4-12.
10. Haq Z, Iqbal Z, Rahman A. Job stress among community health workers: a multi-method study from Pakistan. *International Journal of Mental Health Systems* [Internet]. 2008 [cited 2 March 2016;2(15). Available from: <http://ijmhs.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1752-4458-2-15>
11. NIPS: Pakistan Demographic and Health Survey 2006-7. Islamabad: National Institute of Population Studies & Marco International Inc; 2008.
12. Jani JV, Schacht CD, Jani IV, Bjune G. Risk factors for incomplete vaccination and missed opportunity for immunization in rural Mozambique. *BMC Public Health.* 2008; 8:161.
13. Tadesse H, Deribrew A, Woldie M. Predictors of defaulting from completion of child immunization in south Ethiopia, May 2008- A case control study. *BMC Public Health.* 2009; 9:150.
14. Cockcroft A, Andersson N, Omer K, Ansari NM, Khan A, Chaudhry UU, Ansari U. One size does not fit all: local determinants of measles vaccination in four districts of Pakistan. *BMC Int Health Hum Rights.* 2009;9(1): S4
15. Rahman M, Obaid-Nasrin S. Factors affecting acceptance of complete immunization coverage of children under five years in rural Bangladesh. *Saludpublica de mexico.* 2010;52(2):134-140
16. Sanou A, Simboro S, Kouyate B, Dugas M, Graham J, Bibeau G. Assessment of factors associated with complete immunization coverage in children aged 12-23 months: A cross sectional study in Nouna District, Burkina Faso. *BMC Int Health Hum Rights.* 2009;9(1): S10.
17. Yasin G. Socio-economic factors affecting the trend towards vaccination of mother and infants in Multan city. *Journal of Research Science Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan Pakistan.* 2004;15(1):107-112.
18. Rosenthal MM, Greiner JR. The Barefoot Doctors of China: from political creation to professionalization. *Hum Organ.* Winter. 1982;41(4):330-341
19. World Development Report 1993: Investing in Health. *Commun Dis Rep CDR Wkly.* 1993; 3:137.
20. Zhu N, Allen E, Kearns A, Caglia J, Atun R. Lady Health Workers in Pakistan [Internet]. 2016 [cited 2 March 2016]. Available from: <https://cdn2.sph.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/17/2014/08/HSPH-Pakistan5.pdf>
21. Rammohan A, Awofeso N, Fernandez RC. Paternal education status significantly influences infants' measles vaccination uptake, independent of maternal education status. *BMC Public Health* 2012; 12:336.
22. Health Infrastructure and Immunization Coverage in Rural India - Proquest. *Search.proquest.com.* N.p. 2016. Web. 2 Apr. 2016.
23. Bryce J. Countdown to 2015 for maternal, newborn, and child survival: the 2008 report on tracking coverage of interventions. *Lancet.* 2008; 371:1247-58.
24. Casey M, Thiede Call K, Klingner J. Are rural residents less likely to obtain recommended preventive healthcare services? *American Journal of Preventive Medicine.* 2001;21(3):182-188.

25. The Express Tribune. Child Mortality: Pakistan tough place for children to stay alive [Internet]. 2013. Available from: <http://tribune.com.pk/story/603985/child-mortality-pakistan-toughplace-for-children-to-stay-alive-says-report/>
26. Millennium Development Goal 4 [Internet]. UNDP. 2013 [cited 9 April 2016]. Available from: http://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/mdg_overview/mdg_goals/mdg4.html
27. Bugvi A, Rahat R, Zakar R, Zakar M, Fischer F, Nasrullah M et al. Factors associated with non-utilization of child immunization in Pakistan: evidence from the Demographic and Health Survey 2006-07. *BMC Public Health*. 2014;14(1):232.
28. Hafeez A, Mohamud B, Riaz M. Lady health workers programme in Pakistan: challenges, achievements and the way forward. *J Pak Med Assoc*. 2011;61(3):210-215.
29. Jokhio A, Winter H, Cheng K. An Intervention Involving Traditional Birth Attendants and Perinatal and Maternal Mortality in Pakistan. *New Eng J Med*. 2005;352(20):2091-2099. [4] UNICEF, State of the world Children,2004, Oxford University Press, New York.